

Synthesis of some 2-(2'-Chlorobenzoyl)coumaran-3-ones[†]

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Syntheses of a few 2-(2'-chlorobenzoyl)coumaran-3-ones (4a-e) have been described following three different routes. In the first route, 2-benzoyloxyacetophenones (2a-e) have been first converted by Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement to the corresponding dibenzoyl compounds (3a-e), the bromination of which followed by cyclisation gave the corresponding coumaran-3-ones (4a-e). In the second route, the esters (2a-e) were first brominated at the α -carbon atom of the acetyl side chain by cupric bromide and then converted directly to the corresponding 4a-e. In the third route, the dibenzoyl compounds (3a-e) have first been converted to the corresponding 3-bromoflavones (7a-e) by bromination and cyclisation, which in turn have been converted into 4a-e. All the coumaran-3-ones obtained by the three routes have been found to be identical.

COUMARAN-3-one derivatives have been reported to possess varying biological activities¹⁻⁵. The literature dealing with synthesis of 2-acyl- or 2-aroil- coumaran-3-ones, however, is limited. A series of systematic investigations leading to the syntheses of 2-heteroacylcoumaran-3-ones have very recently been reported from this laboratory⁶⁻⁸. In view of known biological activity enhancing effect of halogen atoms and methyl group, it was proposed to prepare a number of 2-aroilcoumaran-3-ones, in which one benzenoid ring invariably contained a chlorine atom and the other methyl and/or halogen atom. The coumaran-3-ones reported herein have been obtained by three different routes. Scheme 1 depicts the first route.

The esters, 2a-e have been obtained in good yields by the reaction of the constituents in dry pyridine using phosphorus oxychloride as the condensing agent^{8,9}. Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement of 2a-e yielded 3a-e, which on bromination at low temperature (0°) followed by cyclisation produced 4a-e. Yields at all stages were high. The elemental analyses and ir spectra¹⁰ of 4a-e confirm their structure.

In Scheme 2, the compounds 5a-e were first obtained from 2a-e. Bromination was smoothly carried out using cupric bromide in dioxane^{8,11}. This reagent brominates the benzoyloxyacetophenone side chain predominantly, even when the ester moiety at position 2 carries such bromination prone rings as furan or thiophene^{7,8}. Cyclisation of 5a-e by boiling their dioxane solution with KOH followed by acidification gave 4a-e, obviously through the unstable products 6a-e (Ref. 12). The compounds 4a-e obtained by this route were identical with those obtained following Scheme 1.

Having obtained authentic samples of the compounds 4a-e, Scheme 3 was designed which not only gives a third route but *inter alia* helps in

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achieving a verification of the contention of Wadokar and Doifode¹⁸.

These authors carried out the bromination of only a very few diketones of the type 3 in dioxan at room temperature and reported to have obtained the corresponding 3-bromoflavones of the type 7 directly which on boiling with ethanolic KOH gave the related 2-aryl coumaran-3-ones (4). In the present case, all the diketones (3a-e) were similarly treated and the bromoflavones (7a-e) were isolated in crystalline form in 40 to 80% yield. Their structures were confirmed by elemental analyses and comparison of their IR spectra with chromones. The bromoflavones (7a-e) were converted into the bromine-free coumaran-3-ones (4a-e) in moderate to good yields by boiling with ethanolic KOH and were identical in all respects with the authentic samples.

Experimental

All melting points were recorded in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (nujol/KBr) were recorded in a Beckmann spectrophotometer.

Benzoyloxyacetophenones (2a-e) : A well cooled mixture of 1a-e (0.0065 mol) and *o*-chlorobenzoic acid (0.007 mol) in dry pyridine (6 ml) was treated with phosphorus oxychloride (0.24 ml) dropwise with constant stirring. The thick pasty mass so obtained was stirred for further 2 h, at 70-80°. The mixture was then cooled to room temperature and decomposed with ice and HCl (2 N). The solid so obtained was triturated with NaOH solution (2%), filtered, washed with water and crystallised from a suitable solvent. Their yields, m.ps. (crystallised from ethanol) and elemental analyses results are as follows : 2a (75%), 80-81° (Found : C, 66.6 ; H, 4.7. C₁₈H₁₃O₃Cl requires C, 66.5, H, 4.5%) ; 2b (70%), 80° (Found : C, 58.3 ; H, 3.1. C₁₅H₁₀O₃Cl requires C, 58.2 ; H, 3.2%) ; 2c (70%), 82-83° (Found : C, 52.4 ; H, 3.3. C₁₆H₁₂O₃ClBr requires C, 52.2 ; H, 3.2%) ; 2d (80%), 112-13° (Found : C, 51.9 ; H, 3.3. C₁₆H₁₂O₃ClBr requires C, 52.2 ; H, 3.2%) ; 2e (60%), 125-26° (Found : C, 46.54 ; H, 2.35. C₁₅H₉O₃ClBr requires C, 46.4 ; H, 2.32%).

2-Hydroxy-2'-chlorodibenzoylmethanes (3a-e) : A solution of 2a-e (0.01 mol) in dry dioxane was treated with powdered KOH (0.03 mol) and the mixture was refluxed gently for 0.5 h avoiding moisture. A yellow solid separated during heating. The cooled mixture was decomposed with ice and H₂SO₄ (2 N). The yellow solid so obtained was filtered, washed and crystallised from ethanol. The yields, m.ps. and elemental analyses results are as follows : 3a (80%), 104-05° (Found : C, 66.6 ; H, 4.52. C₁₈H₁₃O₃Cl requires C, 66.5 ; H, 4.5%) ; 3b (70%), 125-26° (Found : C, 57.9 ; H, 3.3. C₁₅H₁₀O₃Cl₂ requires C, 58.2 ; H, 3.2%) ; 3c (80%), 136-37° (Found : C, 52.4 ; H, 3.1. C₁₆H₁₂O₃ClBr requires C, 52.2 ; H, 3.2%) ; 3d (75%), 115-16° (Found : C, 52.1 ; H, 3.3. C₁₆H₁₂O₃ClBr requires C, 52.2 ; H, 3.2%) ; 3e (80%), 152-53° (Found : C, 46.3 ; H, 2.2. C₁₅H₉O₃Cl₂Br requires C, 46.4 ; H, 2.3%).

Coumaran-3-ones (4a-e) from the diketones (3a-e) : To a stirred solution of diketone (3a-e ; 0.001 mol) in dry chloroform (15 ml) was added a solution of bromine (molar proportion) in dry chloroform (5 ml) at 0° in presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃. Stirring was continued till the colour of bromine disappeared. The mixture was then refluxed on water-bath for 3 h, cooled and acidified with dilute HCl. The chloroform layer was then separated, washed and dried (MgSO₄). On removal of chloroform a solid was obtained which was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

***ω*-Bromochlorobenzoyloxyacetophenones (5a-e) :** A mixture of finely powdered dry cupric bromide (0.01 mol) and anhydrous dioxane (20 ml) was refluxed for 0.5 h to get a clear solution. The ester (2a-e ; 0.005 mol) was then added to the solution and refluxing was continued for 3 to 4 h. The appearance of grey white precipitate of copper(II) bromide at the bottom of the flask indicated the completion of the reaction. The mixture was then cooled and filtered. The filtrate was poured slowly into water (10 ml) and the precipitated solid was filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol. The yields, m.ps. and elemental analyses results are as follows : 5a, gummy mass from which crystals

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF COUMARAN-3-ONES (4)

Compd. no.	Name of compd.*	M.p. °C	Yield** %	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)		ν_{max} cm ⁻¹
				C	H	
4a	5-Methyl-2-(2'-B) C	124-25	60,45,55	67.01 (67.22)	3.84 (3.73)	2960, 1608
4b	5-Chloro-2-(2'-B) C	142-43	55,45,60	58.63 (58.54)	2.61 (2.63)	2950, 1608
4c	5-Bromo-7-methyl-2-(2'-B) C	136-37	60,55,50	52.53 (52.61)	2.74 (2.62)	3100, 1605
4d	5-Methyl-7-bromo-2-(2'-B) C	121-22	50,50,60	52.53 (52.61)	2.68 (2.62)	1608
4e	5-Chloro-7-bromo-2-(2'-B) C	163-65	70,80,70	46.63 (46.55)	1.81 (1.92)	2950, 1610

*B = Chlorobenzoyl ; C = coumaran-3-one.

**Obtained by the first, second and third routes, respectively.

could not be obtained; 5b (60%), 98-99° (Found: C, 46.4; H, 2.35. $C_{15}H_9O_3Cl_2Br$ requires C, 46.3; H, 2.3%); 5c (52%), 66-67° (Found: C, 42.8; H, 2.4. $C_{15}H_{11}O_3ClBr_2$ requires C, 43.3; H, 2.46%); 5d (72%), 111-12° (Found: C, 43.2; H, 2.35. $C_{15}H_{11}O_3ClBr_2$ requires C, 43.0; H, 2.46%); 5e (65%), 130-31° (Found: C, 38.6; H, 1.8. $C_{15}H_9O_3Cl_2Br_2$ requires C, 38.55; H, 1.72%).

Compounds 4a-e from ω -bromoesters (5a-e): A mixture of a ω -bromoester (0.005 mol) in dry dioxane (15 ml) and powdered KOH (0.015 mol) was refluxed for 0.5 h. After cooling, the contents were poured over ice-dilute H_2SO_4 mixture and the resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

3-Bromoflavones (7a-e): *o*-Hydroxy dibenzoyl methane (3a-e; 0.01 mol) was dissolved in anhydrous dioxane (30 ml), and bromine (0.05 ml) was added dropwise to the stirred solution. Stirring was continued for 3 h. The reaction mixture on pouring into a large volume of water yielded the desired compounds which were crystallised from ethanol (Table 2). They analyse correctly for carbon and hydrogen.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF 3-BROMOFLAVONES (7)

Compd no.	Name of compd.*	M.p. °C	Yield %	ν_{max} (cm^{-1})	
				C=O	C=C
7a	2-(2'-P)-6-methyl-F	113-14	40	1645	1614
7b	2-(2'-P)-6-chloro-F	155-56	80	1645	1605
7c	2-(2'-P)-6-bromo-8-methyl-F	154-55	55	1680	1618
7d	2-(2'-P)-6-methyl-8-bromo-F	146-48	62	1645	1615
7e	2-(2'-P)-6-chloro-8-bromo-F	181-82	78	1650	1600

*P = Chlorophenyl; F = bromoflavone.

Compounds 4a-e from 7a-e: 3-Bromoflavone (7a-e; 0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (30 ml), and ethanolic KOH (10 ml, 25%) was added to it. The mixture was gently refluxed for 2 h, and then cooled and poured into a mixture of ice and HCl (2 N). The desired coumaran-3-ones (4a-e)

separated as solid was filtered, washed, dried and crystallised from ethanol. The crystalline products obtained (Table 1) were identical with the coumaran-3-ones prepared by the previous routes.

The *o*-hydroxyacetophenones were obtained by the methods available in literature¹⁴⁻¹⁷ and the nuclear brominated hydroxyacetophenones were obtained by the method of Buu-Hoi and Lavit¹⁸.

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